

КЕЙС СТАДИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ КАК ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫЙ МЕТОД ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ КОММУНИКАТИВНЫХ НАВЫКОВ

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CASE STUDY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING AS AN INTERACTIVE METHOD OF FORMING COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS

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Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются особенности и значение метода кейс-стади как интерактивного метода формирования коммуникативных навыков у студентов. В статье обсуждается роль кейс-стади в процессе обучения языку, характерные черты, типы, структура и технологии.

Цель исследования – проанализировать особенности кейс-стади и рекомендовать его к использованию в качестве интерактивного метода формирования коммуникативных навыков студентов. В данной статье авторы попытались определить кейс-стади, дать типы классификации, основные черты, этапы, ряд практических рекомендаций по выполнению кейсов, компетенции, которые необходимо развивать при использовании метода кейс-стади, общие технологии использования в классе, преимущества и недостатки в организации кейса на занятиях и примеры кейс-заданий для применения в учебном процессе.

Методы исследования – описательный, сравнительный, аналитический и прагматический анализ. Методология исследования – аналитический обзор существующих идей по описываемой теме и личные взгляды как специалиста в данной области. Статья полностью практическая касается сути и важных особенностей в организации кейс-стади в процессе обучения английскому языку. С помощью сравнения и сопоставления были определены и предложены технологии, плюсы и минусы кейс-стади.

В качестве научной новизны и практических результатов исследовательской работы были разработаны пять образцов заданий кейс-стади для использования на занятиях по преподаванию английского языка. В качестве выводов статьи мы подтверждаем, что кейс-стади является эффективным инструментом для развития коммуникативных навыков студентов, поскольку это активное обсуждение и взаимодействие, в котором студенты могут развивать говорение, дискуссию, критическое мышление и критическое размышление на основе реальных жизненных ситуаций.

Abstract

The article under research deals with features and importance of case-study method as interactive method to form communicative skills of the students. The article discusses the role of case studies in language teaching process, characteristic features, types, structure and technologies.

The aim of the research study is to analyze the features of case-study and to recommend it to use as the interactive method that form communicative skills of students. In the given article, the authors tried to define a case study, to give the basic classification types, the main features, stages, a number of practical recommendations relevant to do cases, competences to be developed in case study method, general technologies of using a case in the classroom, advantages and disadvantages in organizing a case at classes, and sample case tasks to apply in teaching process.

The research methods are descriptive, comparative, analytical and pragmatic analysis. The research methodology is analytical research review of existed ideas on the described topic, and personal viewpoints as the specialist in the given field. The article is fully practical concerns on the essence and important features in organizing case studies in English teaching process. With the help of comparison and contrast the technologies, pros and cons of case study were defined and suggested.

As the scientific novelty and practical results of the research work there were developed five samples of case study tasks to use in English teaching classes. As the conclusions of the research article we confirm that case-study

is effective tool to develop students' communicative skills as it is an active discussion and interaction where students can develop speaking, discussion, critical thinking, and critical reflection based on real life situations.

Ключевые слова: кейс стади, владение языком, коммуникативные навыки, интерактивный метод, сотрудничество, демо-кейс, интерактивный кейс, решения, межкультурная коммуникация, аутентичные материалы.

Keywords: case study, language proficiency, communicative skill, interactive method, cooperation, demo case, interactive case, solutions, intercultural communication, authentic materials.

Introduction

For teachers of foreign languages and educators it is a task to find effective teaching techniques or methods that develop students' language skills, especially communicative skills. Case-study is a powerful resource that solve the given problem. Case-study method is one of the interactive methods in language teaching that help the students to interact in a group or individually, to acquire communication skills. The goal of a case-study is discussion in cooperation of a problem, analysis of different cases or situations, and development of practical solutions.

The article under review deals with the case-study technology or method as one of the methods that help to develop students' communicative competence, interactivity, and speaking abilities. Case-study method is very practical tool to develop students' speaking, working in groups, to apply what they have gained theoretically in practice, to understand complex problems. Case-study not only helps to improve language skills as it is used in English teaching process, but also teaches to work with real-life situations, develops critical thinking, and making real practical decisions. Analyzing case studies, students learn to weigh different options, risks, it involves cultural contexts, for this reason encourages cultural awareness.

Case-technology as active form of learning makes students work actively, gaining deep knowledge and comprehension. One more importance and benefit of case-studies is facilitating new solutions and innovative approaches, foster critical thinking. When selecting case-studies teachers should pay attention to students' level, interest, and objectives of the studied material and topic of the discussion.

For the last years case technology is becoming popular in language teaching classrooms together with fields as medicine, business, economics and politics. It is not a new thing in language learning, but it is commonly used today. The reasons of it we indicated in the research article, and tried to give its essence, practical importance, and role in language learning. It possesses several objectives in teaching as developing speaking skills, teaching to make right decisions, deeply understanding the cases and realizing their solutions, and improves language proficiency, understanding cultural context.

Case study technology is very important and effective teaching method which is oriented to analyze, to solve and to discuss real lively situations. And it is used in teaching process as one of the effective methods that facilitate to develop communicative competences of students. Case study develops students' analytical, critical thinking. Case study is considered to be an approach or a method which is oriented to in-depth analysis of real-life situations.

Case-studies are the scenarios that apply the concepts learned in the classroom in the real-life situation. They are presented in narrative form, and often include problem solving, links to some course readings or raw materials, discussions by groups of students or the whole class. The case-studies are more effective when they are presented sequentially, students receive additional information depending on the situation and can continue to analyze or criticize the situation or the problem [1, p. 292].

Professor Paul Lawrence gives characteristics of case-study and definition. He defines it as a reality which are brought into the classroom in order to work, discuss for the students and teachers. These are real-life situations to be discussed in detail in class to form communication forum [2, p.75].

According to history and origin the case study is widely used in clinical fields such as psychology and medicine. It is investigations of particular cases and in-depth study of the cases under consideration, analysis of the cases under study [3].

Case-study needs deep exploration and understanding what is happening in real life, and needs to study these situations from different perspectives [4, p.21].

Case-study approach or method is used in different disciplines, it is devoted to analyze or study one phenomenon, especially it is popular in business English. In any case, cases we can also use in English classes in order to teach to communication, to do research, to examine something and express their points of view. There are steps that case study will be efficient and successful: to give time to students to read and think about the case; to introduce the case, give certain steps or instructions how to do or follow the case; to form groups to discuss the case and ask them to work cooperatively, everybody should be involved in discussion, to set roles to each student; to ask the group to give their solutions or decisions, to write conclusions; to ask questions to clarify some points, to examine their assumptions; to synthesize issues.

A.S. Eremin pointed out in his work, initially, Harvard Business School cases were characterized by the following features [5, p. 4]:

- a) there were real situations/cases obtained as a result of establishing relations with real companies;
- b) the case is based on a specific problem that can be solved;
- b) the description of the case is carried out from the point of view of the decision-making manager;
- c) the case description contains information about various aspects of the company;
- d) cases do not always contain detailed information on solving the problem;

e) cases may not contain questions that help in the process of solving the problem;

g) cases may differ in description and scope of work [6, p. 97].

The case-study method adheres to the general goals and objectives of education, including: 1) learning the content and developing professional knowledge, skills and abilities at the required level; 2) development of the student as a person; 3) the ability to develop a generalized solution, taking into account alternatives; 4) planning activities; 5) aims to predict their consequences.

According to Stephen Krashen, the distinctive feature of the case study in professional foreign language learning is the use of authentic language material in the course of study, which always requires active skills from students in individual and group work [7]. At the same time, the negative characteristics of a case study include the following: 1) a large number of additional literature to be read on a certain topic to form basic knowledge; 2) texts that are difficult in terms of language and content; 3) complex conceptual concepts that require considerable time expenditure; 4) situations usually include westernized concepts that are not always used in practice; 5) when solving a real problem, the main attention of students is directed not to a foreign language, but to checking data and performing a professional task through it.

Case studies include three main stages: 1) data entry; 2) processing and working with data; 3) presentation of conclusions. Working with data, in turn, can be divided into stages such as 1) understanding and using data; 2) analysis; 3) use of professional skills and qualifications; 4) examination of alternative methods in the process of decision-making on a given issue.

Case study materials contain a brief description of the problem situation, including: 1) the main direction and activity of the company in question; 2) types of organizations where the skills acquired in the process of reviewing the situation can be used; 3) categories of tasks to be solved by students; 4) requirements for the personal qualities, skills and work methods of a specialist in this specific professional field; 5) list of job duties; 6) educational requirements.

Elements of the case: every case has a name or sphere or type; short description what the case is about; aims or objectives of the case; certain format or structure of the case; tasks to fulfill to the case; detailed questions for discussion; requirements to implement and present case results; for independent study of cases will be given list of sources and information on them.

Additional elements of the case methods which are prepared for tutors include: 1) the date of the case; 2) permission to publish and use the information provided in the case for educational purposes; 3) description of the target group (level of preparation of the student); 4) logic of problem analysis and proof; 5) answers to questions for discussion; 6) epilogue (level of development of the situation considered in the case); 7) warnings (case use experience); 8) links to additional information resources (for self-training of tutors).

Non-textual material in a case study usually includes: 1) visual appendices (drawings, graphs, tables,

photographs); 2) accompany the discussion with a slide; 3) audio and video materials (interviews, video materials); 4) inviting characters who took part in case-studies or visiting their work place; 5) computer modeling.

The use of case-study method in teaching requires certain planning of the lesson. There are some stages or steps to work with cases in class. *First stage* is called confrontation, it means that the teacher informs the topic, sets aims and objectives, and introduces with the case itself. *On the second stage* students have to collect certain information on observed and studied materials. Collected information are presented in the form of diagram, tables, schemes or presentations. *The third stage* is called resolution, it means that students have to answer the questions of the teacher which are prepared beforehand, and be ready to give solutions or decisions on the problem. *The fourth stage* is the discussion or dispute on the presented solutions. Here students can work in groups, can suggest different decisions, and they listen to each other's opinions or ideas and suggest the proper solutions. Finally, *the fifth stage* working with the case is reflection. In reflection stage students give conclusions, reflections on what they have learnt from each other, what solutions they liked most and why, and how it impacted on their speaking competences.

Cases can be classified according to their structure, size, complexity, context and practicality.

According to the level of complexity cases are divided into:

- 1) cases for schoolchildren;
- 2) cases for students;
- 3) cases for postgraduate students and others.

In Western practice, the following types of case studies are considered: demonstration or demo cases, training and innovative.

The purpose of the *demo case* is to show proven methods of solving problems of different categories of complexity, to generalize management practices based on structural facts.

The *training case* aims to gain experience, develop management solutions, and use social technologies through the analysis of simple and complex structural problem situations.

The purpose of the *innovative case* is to develop analytical skills in the analysis of complex but poorly structured situations that have not been solved or are not completed during the preparation of the relevant case [8, p. 46].

In addition, a group of scientists now offers the following types of cases: *problem cases* (the problem of the case is determined in advance, and students face the case for the first time), *design cases* (having a special program aimed at solving the problems in the situation), *illustrative cases* (problem solutions are given, the student's task is to describe the solutions given to solve the problem and determine its advantages and disadvantages), *open cases* (does not require a specific question, algorithms are given to solve the problem facing the *system cases* (a real system is given, students make suggestions for its improvement), *iceberg cases* (the student does not have specific information, to solve

the problem they collect information themselves, search), *serial cases* (an incomplete set of cases is presented, the next case is the previous one case will be continued), *classic cases* (Harvard Business School cases, i.e. business cases), *tactical and strategic cases* (requires a specific strategy and tactics in solving it), *micro, mini, general cases* (small, general cases), *illustrative learning cases* (has specific questions, observes the work of well-known productions, companies, describes them, gives specific solutions).

Methods and materials

The research methods are descriptive, comparative, analytical and pragmatic analysis. The research methodology is analytical research review of existed ideas on the described topic, and personal viewpoints as the specialist in the given field. The article is fully practical concerns on the essence and important features in organizing case studies in English teaching process. The authors have given their professional points of view on the organization and teaching a language using case studies to develop communicative competences of the students. With the help of comparison and contrast the technologies, pros and cons of case study were defined and suggested as the results of the research. Five samples of case study tasks were developed and given sample methods to fulfill the cases.

Results and discussion

A quality case should follow the next requirements: 1) meet the specific goal of its of creation; 2) having a degree of difficulty; 3) depicting several aspects of real life; 4) does not get old too quickly; 4) existence of national color; 5) description of typical situations; 5) development of analytical thinking; 6) is capable of creating a discussion; 7) demonstration of conformity of theory to practice; 8) suitable for the student’s independent reading and discussion; 9) suitable for joint discussion in class under the guidance of the teacher; 10) must adhere to the principle of in making decisions or solving the problems discussion will be important.

The content of the case should meet the following requirements: 1) scope of the case; 2) tasks to be solved with the help of the case; 3) characteristics of the audience to be taught (age, level of education, required level of education); 4) number of listeners; 5) allocation of time according to work stages: independent study, group work, discussion, conclusion. One of the most important issues in the technology of creating cases is the issue of the form of presentation of the collected material. The problem of choosing a presentation style usually arises for novice authors. They need a lot of time to decide which style to use: formal, academic or colloquial.

A number of recommendations are relevant here:

1) the case text should be written in the correct

language (professional editorial work is required before publication); 2) authors should carefully choose their words in order to correctly understand the meaning of the given situation; 3) to increase the lively feature of the case (must meet life or real situations), it is necessary to describe the situation in the past tense (indicating the exact date of the case); 4) it is necessary to use a tabular form of data presentation (summary tables, diagrams, pictures, etc.); 5) it is necessary to carefully check all digital data provided in the case text; 6) reference material used for illustrative purposes will be given in the appendices.

The following competences are formed in using the case study method:

1. Rational (ability to think clearly and logically, analyze information, separate data from information);
2. Practical (ability to combine the theoretical knowledge acquired in the audience in practice, to solve the problem in a practical sense);
3. Creative (comprehensive discussion, inclusion of one’s creativity, quickness of thought and ability to formalize it);
4. Communicative (discussion skills, ability to defend one’s point of view, ability to convince listeners, ability to give concrete solutions, ability to use effective and impressive vocabulary);
5. Social (self-esteem, the ability to listen and appreciate, to protect or oppose a colleague, the ability to behave, the ability to communicate with the environment);
6. Self-differentiation (assessing the situation, finding an optimal solution, distinguishing between theory and practice).

General teaching technologies of using a case in the classroom:

Students should look through, study and discuss case studies, which are written and prepared for study. The performance of the case is carried out under the guidance of the teacher.

The teacher in advance: a) selects a case; b) determines basic and auxiliary materials; b) creates a scenario. The students should analyze the given case, look through the list of required literature, and gets ready to present the case suggestions.

The teacher must: a) help students to discuss the case in advance; b) organize group tasks according to certain roles; c) ask the students to understand the case itself.

Student:

a) asks a question; b) offers solutions; b) makes a decision; c) gives a written report on the work.

The next table shows the technology of case analysis:

Table 1.

Technology of case analysis	
I. Generalization	A brief statement of what is happening in the situation. What’s going on? With whom and why? What is the result of the development of events?
II. Formulate the problem	A short one-sentence text (9-10 words) showing the essence of

	the problem.
III. Participants of the event	a) People - all participants of events, their role, status, characteristics (very briefly); b) Organizations - trying to provide a comprehensive description of the organization in which the events are taking place - its nature, nature of business, external environment and specific features
IV. Chronology of events (practical)	Presentation of facts and events without evaluation and in reverse chronological order.
V. Conceptual issues	Conceptual issues raised in the case. For example, it can be conceptual aspects of motivation, planning, labor and personnel evaluation, etc. The identification of the conceptual aspect must be accompanied by «confirmation» with the facts.
VI. Alternative solutions	A list of possible actions. Justify and evaluate each alternative. Indicator of positive and negative consequences of implementation.
VII. Recommendations	A clear and precise description of the chosen course of action. Explain the reasons and rationale for choosing the course.
VIII. Action plan (first steps)	Briefly and clearly describe the first steps in implementing a course of action that will lead to a solution to the problem.

The features, benefits and challenges of the case study method in English teaching classrooms are shown in the table below:

Table 2.

Advantages and disadvantages of the case study method

Case study method	
Pros	Cons
Focused on the analysis of real practical situations.	Infrequent and effective use of the case study method in school programs.
Students are able to distinguish, analyze and propose solutions independently.	Absence of a collection of educational cases used in the educational process.
Develops the skills of students to work in pairs and groups.	Lack or little experience of English language teachers in conducting case lectures.
It is based on the formation of students' creativity skills.	Absence of a well-established algorithm for solving the case.
Cases are taken from real life, real professional field.	Lack of opportunities to go to business institutions, companies, organize meetings, conduct interviews, get acquainted with their problems, depending on the case situation, in order to provide the right solution.
Case studies are one of the interactive learning tools.	Inability of the teacher to correctly organize specific roles in the lesson in solving the case.
Uses the theoretical knowledge received in the lecture in practice, combines theory and practice.	Organized only in upper classes with a high level of English..
Students will have the opportunity to realize their ideas.	It is best to organize case-solving English classes only with high school students or students, because the language level must be high.
The case-study method develops the creative thinking of the teacher and creates an opportunity to expand the creative ability to create the content of the lesson in a unique way.	According to research, the case method is not often used in schools.
Using this method, it is possible to form the following life skills in the younger generation: creativity, activity, social responsibility, clarity of thought, high professional level literacy, priority of interest incognitive activities	Case-studies can be long or not clear at all, it takes time.
Its value is that students learn to work in a team. They analyze data and jointly develop management solutions.	There is no correct answer in solutions, they can be just possible suggestions.

A case study provides an opportunity to apply theory in practice. By working in groups, students learn to listen to different points of view and to consider them. They also learn to present their solutions, providing arguments to defend their position.	
Strengthens the student's ability to think critically	

As the practical part of our research results, we suggest the following case tasks for learners to fulfill in English language classrooms.

Case №1

Research subject: Learning English for entering to study at the Master Course

Research period: one month

Student's background: Askar is an office manager at business organization in Almaty. He has been working at the business office for more than 6 years. He wants to develop his work-related skills entering to Master Course. But he has no idea on entering issues, what exams to pass, how to get a high score. He wants to search a net after the work when he is at home, unfortunately he is tired after a hard work, do not find a suitable time.

Tasks:

1. Analyze the reasons why Askar could not find time to study entering issues to Master Degree.
2. Find out his business and personal skills or characteristics interviewing him.
3. Suggest possible ways to enter to Master Course and to improve certain skills.

Questions to analyze reasons:

- 1) What do you know about the organization you are working to?
- 2) Say your three strengths and weaknesses.
- 3) What do you value most in your job? And why?
- 4) What are the reasons of your decision to gain a Master's Degree?
- 5) How do you organize your time usually?
- 6) How do the employers characterize you as an office manager?
- 7) What university did you graduate from, and what specialty?

Case №2

Research subject: Difficulties in learning subjects at school

Research period: two months

Student's background: Helen's parents work at big joint stock company as managers. They are very busy and cannot pay special attention to Helen's learning. Helen is the only child in the family. Helen's parents expect many things and bright future for her. Helen's achievements at school are not good. She is one of the difficult learners at her school, in her studies, especially languages.

Tasks:

1. Analyze the reasons why Helen is not good at school with her subjects.
2. Analyze her relationship with her parents and fellow students at school.
3. Find out her progress on definite subjects at school.

4. Analyze the advantages and disadvantages of being an only child in the family.

5. Attend Helen's school to interview her teachers and fellow students.

6. Attend Helen's parents to interview about Helen and her personality.

7. Suggest possible decisions to the problem.

Questions to analyze reasons:

- 1) What character traits do the parents value in their daughter?
- 2) Do you like or dislike being an only child in the family?
- 3) Are you good at with your classmates?
- 4) Do the parents sacrifice their time to their child?
- 5) What are her progresses at school? Are there any of them?

Case №3

Research subject: Problems the rookie teachers might face

Research period: two months

Student's background: Suppose you're a rookie teacher at the university after graduation of your Master's degree. You come to class to conduct seminar classes. Students treat you too young, think that you are not experienced, you cannot organize good lessons. You are in hesitation, and want to some recommendations to organize your classroom.

Tasks:

1. List out the problems a rookie teacher might face.
 2. Analyze each problem and seek possible solutions.
 3. Read special issues about classroom management.
 4. Learn the students' behaviors.
 5. Attend experienced teachers' classes to improve some skills.
 6. Think over possible teacher development courses you might attend in the nearest future.
 7. Suggest possible decisions to the problem.
- Questions to analyze reasons:*
- 1) What kind of work-related skills do you have?
 - 2) What are your strengths and weaknesses?
 - 3) What subjects you are specialized at the Master's Degree?
 - 4) Do the subjects you studied at the university help you organize your class?
 - 5) What are the key roles of a teacher in the classroom?
 - 6) What makes a teacher special?
 - 7) Have you ever attended classes of other teachers?

8) Did you read any special methodological issues before the class?

Case №4

Research subject: Problems the rookie teachers might face

Research period: two months

Student's background: You have conducted the lecture on one of the theoretical subjects. And the experienced teacher participated and observed your lecture. She did not like your teaching technique on that subject. And she says that it is the way they have always been taught, nothing new.

Tasks:

1. List out the problems a rookie teacher might face.
2. Analyze each problem and seek possible solutions.
3. Read special issues about classroom management.
4. Learn the students' behaviors.
5. Attend experienced teachers' classes to improve some skills.
6. Think over possible teacher development courses you might attend in the nearest future.
7. Compare the structure of theoretical and practical subjects.
8. Suggest possible decisions to the problem.

Questions to analyze reasons:

- 1) What differentiates theoretical and practical classes?
- 2) What are your strengths and weaknesses?
- 3) Is criticism all right for you, and what is your attitude to it?
- 4) What would you do and react to the comments which are given by fellow teachers who are considered to be experienced?
- 5) What kind of interactive techniques can you apply in class?
- 6) What makes a teacher special?
- 7) Have you ever attended classes of other teachers?
- 8) Did you read any special methodological issues before the class?
- 9) What are the innovative teaching methods in modern classroom?
- 10) What teaching methods you found interactive and communicative when you attended classes of other teachers?

Case №5

Research subject: Problems of corporal punishment at school

Research period: two months

Student's background: Is teacher uses corporal punishment often in his or her classes, students cannot be active or involved in the lessons. Students do not have their own voice or freedom to speak, and they speak in case only when the teacher asks something. Because of this situation in class, students do not speak even in outside to express their opinions. They stay calm, shy and they do not feel free.

What is your attitude to such physical discipline? Is it necessary in your culture?

Tasks:

1. Find out advantages and disadvantages of corporal punishment at school.
2. List out cultural features of corporal punishment.
3. Attend the classes and observe if corporal punishment take place in them.
4. Learn the students' behaviors.
5. Analyze the common reasons that corporal punishment take place.
6. Compare and contrast school system in your country and abroad
7. Suggest possible decisions to the problem.

Questions to analyze reasons:

- 1) Does corporal punishment take place in your culture?
- 2) What are the attitudes of society and people in your culture to corporal punishment?
- 3) Is it good idea using corporal punishment at school?
- 4) How to you usually punish your students if they are not ready for class?
- 5) Being a strict teacher is it advantage or disadvantage?

Conclusion

It is very appropriate to use the case study method among high school students, because an adult learner begins to be guided by consciously set goals, strives to deepen knowledge in a certain field, strives to learn independently. Students begin to work regularly with additional literature. Systematization of knowledge in various subjects, establishment of interdisciplinary connections is typical for the educational process. If pupils are eager to clarify about the object, then, a high school student tries to understand different ideas or opinions on this question, to form an opinion, to determine the truth. They love to research and experiment, to create new originality and innovation, they are interested not only in theoretical problems, but also in the analysis itself, in the way of evidence. Students like the fact that the instructor makes them choose a decision between different points of view, demands to justify some conclusions. They argue with teachers and stubbornly defend their position. Due to these characteristics, the case study method will be typical for teenagers of this age, we believe that their ability to provide a clear solution to the problem will be sufficient.

In our opinion, according to special studies, the scope of education in the upper class expands, students begin to look at the lesson consciously. A high school student confidently uses various mental operations in the learning process, thinks logically, and remembers. Thus, the characteristic features of adolescence are: inner freedom, ethical idealism and maximalism, aesthetic idealism, the desire to recognize and recreate reality, selflessness in obsession, charity and faith, the artistic, creative nature of reality perception.

One of the key pros of the case method is that the students are interested and involved in the end or finalizing the task. This is due to the uniqueness of each story, the natural connection of the described situation with life, independent thinking and freedom of thought

of students. Active discussion of the situation with classmates gives the foreign language lesson a conversational format focused on active interaction of students with each other, during which there are no planned judgments, most of the justification can appear in the process of communication. This lesson is different from the traditional lesson where most of the time students learn factual knowledge.

Due to these reasons, in our article, we studied this case study method as a communicative, interactive author's methodology used in learning a foreign language, tried to show its main points, and in the future, we recommend that high school students use this method more often in English classes, we decided to compile a case assignment within the framework of various topics.

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